

NANO-ENABLED MANUFACTURING OF AEROSPACE-GRADE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Aerospace manufacturers continue to rely on composite materials to make aerovehicles lighter and stronger, particularly employing carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) using carbon microfiber reinforcement with thermoset and thermoplastic polymer matrices. With the increasing use of such composites, the need for energy-efficient, cost-effective methods to produce composite structures is desired. Traditional curing processes such as autoclaves and ovens rely on convective heat transfer, which has fundamental inefficiencies and several limitations including infrastructure cost and throughput bottlenecks. Similarly, hot presses (usually for thermoplastic matrices) for processing composites through conductive heat transfer are limited to a narrow range of part geometries. Direct Joule heating with carbon nanotube (CNT) film network heaters has shown significant promise to overcome these key manufacturing challenges of composites in the aerospace industry. This Out-of-Oven (OoO) conductive curing technique has been shown to cure aerospace-grade out-of-autoclave (OoA) CFRP prepreg laminates with equivalent quality to that achieved with the manufacturer's recommend cure cycle (MRCC) using an oven. The first application of OoO heating to processing aerospace-grade thermoplastic (polyetheretherketone, PEEK) CFRP prepreg is presented in this work. OoO heating is found to produce PEEK CFRP plate specimens comparable or better than MRCC hot press-produced laminates, both in terms of quality and strength, with advantages in spatial and temporal control noted.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aerospace original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) currently have a renewed interest in using thermoplastic prepreps in the production of aircraft parts due to their superior mechanical properties, recyclability, and ease of storage compared to their thermoset counterparts. As with thermosets, thermoplastics are thermally processed in autoclaves and ovens, but are most typically formed in hot presses. There are several disadvantages associated with convective heat transfer through these heating chambers, as well as limitations in part shapes for hot press molding. For aerospace structural parts that require an autoclave, there is uncertainty in maintaining a constant spatial heat flux and uniform temperature to achieve uniform part properties and minimize residual stresses. For large parts, such as a composite wing or fuselage, the lack of heating uniformity can lead to variations in the strength properties throughout the structural component.

The Out-of-Oven (OoO) method shows great promise towards manufacturing efficiency and minimizing part quality variation. The OoO process is both compatible and advantageous for the processing of thermoplastic prepreps: first, the chemical vapor deposition-grown (CVD) carbon nanotube (CNT) film heater used in Lee et al.'s study can generate temperatures up to 550 °C, which is necessary to produce aerospace-grade thermoplastic composites; second, the commercial CNT film provides uniform temperature over the area that it heats; and third, OoO curing allows for relatively precise control over the temperature of the laminate as it is being cured. Lee et al. demonstrated the

viability of the OoO method focusing on curing thermoset out-of-autoclave material systems via OoO in comparison to traditional methods. The main contribution of this work is to assess whether OoO curing can be applied to thermoplastic aerospace-grade composites, despite their higher temperature processing requirement (400 °C) relative to epoxy matrix systems that cure at 180 °C.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In prior work, small quantities of vertically-aligned carbon nanotubes (VACNTs) were produced for OoO research via CVD [1]. Here, we are utilizing commercial CNT films, which are now readily available in sheet form at the 30 cm x 30 cm (12" x 12") scale. Given that commercial CNTs have not been used before for this kind of study, two qualifying tests were designed to assess the material for the OoO curing of thermoplastics. The first test determines the thermal stability of the CNT film in air at a temperature slightly higher than the maximum dwell temperature, 400 °C, of the CF/PEEK prepreg. The second test quantifies the maximum temperature of the CNT film in ambient conditions looking towards other higher-temperature polymers and heating applications for the CNT films. The CVD-grown VACNT films showed thermal stability in the 550 °C range in air, so they are appropriate for CF/PEEK OoO processing.

Three patches of commercially produced thin, dry CNT film called Veelo HEAT from General Nano LLC were tested in the thermal stability experiment. The film has an areal weight of 25 gsm, a thickness of 10 µm, and an isotropic sheet resistance of 0.25 Ω/sq. The patches were 20 mm in length and 15 mm in width. The Conductive Copper Foil Electrical Tape (product #76555A721) is from McMaster Carr with a thickness of 89 µm (0.0035"). The test apparatus consisted of a 6.35 mm (1/4") thick quartz square substrate with two strips of copper tape laid on the top surface of the plate, spaced roughly 8 mm each other from the inner edges of each strip. The small CNT patch was laid on top of the two strips, with care taken to have as much contact as possible between the left and right edges of the CNT patch and the copper strips to conduct current properly. With the patch in place, two more copper strips were laid directly on top of the first two strips and CNT patch, thus fixing the thin film in place. Two more quarter-inch-thick quartz substrates were placed on the copper strip and CNT patch layup on each side, and then each was fixed with a metal clamp to ensure contact between the two materials. The ends of the copper strips extending from the quartz substrate had wires attached to them. These wires were connected to the positive and negative terminals of the BK Precision 9201 power supply. A strip of silica tape was placed underneath the wires attached to the copper strip to prevent an electrical short from occurring.

Once the apparatus was set up, the power supply would be turned on. A FLIR T640 camera was set up to capture the thermal profile of the CNT patch as current flows through the circuit. The thermal camera's software was used to focus the camera lens on the CNT film patch's area so the temperature of the film would only be recorded. Within the patch area, the point corresponding to the highest temperature was selected for sampling. The voltage from the power supply would be increased every 5 minutes until the temperature on the thermal camera detected 420 °C at the center of the specimen. This rate of increase had no observable effect on the CNT film. The voltage was raised to roughly 8 volts to generate a temperature of 420 °C, with an observed current of ~1.6 Amperes. The temperature would be held for an hour, which is double the time recommended for fabricating a thermoplastic laminate in a static hot press. The reason for choosing an hour was to ensure that the CNT film could maintain temperature for an extended period.

While the power supply and thermal camera were on, the voltage, current, power, and temperature were recorded on a laptop via universal serial bus (USB). The voltage, current, and power were sampled at 1 Hz, and the temperature at 10 Hz. For each CNT patch to be considered viable for OoO thermoplastic processing, the current could not drop significantly (more than 0.5 Amperes) or go to zero throughout the hour-long dwell at 420 °C, and the recorded temperature could not dip below 400 °C. A summary of the test results is found in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the Thermal Stability and Max Temperature test key results.

Thermal Stability and Max Temperature Tests Results Summary			
Specimen	Starting Temperature (°C)	Ending Temperature (°C)	Max Temperature (°C)
Patch #1	426	425	556
Patch #2	425	443	562
Patch #3	424	429	557

After qualifying the efficacy of the commercial CNT film via the thermal stability and max temperature tests, OoO heating is applied to the PEEK-HTS45 system. The setup for processing thermoplastic plate samples to fabricate specimens relied on a vacuum bag only (VBO) technique, termed simply OoO here. These will be compared to autoclave and hot-press processed PEEK CFRP. A 305 mm (12”) x 305 mm (12”) x 3.175 mm (.125”) base aluminum plate is used as the foundation of the VBO setup (see Fig. 4.8). On top of the aluminum base/caul plate, a 152 mm (6”) x 152 mm (6”) x 25 mm (1”) block of calcium silicate is placed to function as a thermal insulator to prevent the base plate from becoming a heat sink. The calcium silicate block from Industrial Insulation Group (IIG) has a thermal conductivity k of $0.115 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}$ [2]. For reference, the aluminum metal tool plates and the CFRP in the through-thickness direction have thermal conductivities k of $175 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}$ and $0.658 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}$, respectively. On top of the block is a layer of Thermalide film, which is a high-temperature bagging material from Airtech International. The Thermalide film has two long strips of copper tape on the left and right edges. Then the Veelo HEAT commercial CNT film with dimensions of 50 mm x 160 mm lies on top of the film and copper tape, with care taken to maximize the area overlap of the left and right sides of the film and the copper tape. Two more strips of copper tape lay directly on top of the film and the bottom two tape strips, securing the film in place to ensure contact with the copper and allowed current to flow smoothly. Another sheet of Thermalide film is laid on top of the tape and film. A 50 mm x 150 mm x 6.25 mm aluminum metal tool plate is placed on top to complete the stack of materials under the laminate. This aluminum metal plate has the laminate-side covered in Thermalide film. This side will be in contact with the bottom ply of the thermoplastic laminate being processed. The high-temperature film is treated with release agent Frekote 700 on the side in contact with the bottom of the laminate. The purpose of applying the release agent is to ensure that no material, particularly the Thermalide film or breather fabric, sticks to the laminate after the vacuum bag cure has finished. The plies of the laminate are then laid one by one on top of the aluminum plate with Thermalide film. Once all the plies are stacked on the plate, a thermocouple rests on the top edge of the top ply.

Then, a second metal tool plate with Thermalide film on one side is placed on top. The Thermalide film on this plate has also been treated with Frekote 700 and is facing down to be in contact with the top ply of the laminate. Next, high-temperature sealant tape A-800-3G (thickness of 3.175 mm (.125”), width of 12.5 mm (.5”), and rated max temperature of 427 °C) from Airtech International is adhered around the perimeter of the thermal insulation on top of the base plate. The copper tape strips are run across the width of the sealant tape to allow for wires to attach to them after the vacuum is pulled in the interior of the setup. The thermocouple used in this experiment is an Omega 5SRTC-GG-K-30-36 Ready Made Insulated Thermocouple. The glass braid insulated wire K-type thermocouple is rated to

endure temperatures of up to 480 °C. More importantly, its bead type design means it has a low thermal mass, so it can obtain the temperature of the laminate at a frequency of 1 Hz. Similarly, the thermocouple wiring is run across the width of the sealant tape, where the connector attaches to a USB reader port. The USB thermocouple reader is then plugged into a laptop or desktop to read the temperature in real time, and the temperature profile of the 18-ply laminate is shown in Figure 1. Note that the 90° flexural beam samples also followed this temperature profile with a dwell time of 40 minutes (per the manufacturer) instead of 30 minutes for the short beam shear (SBS) & dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) samples, to allow the plies to thoroughly consolidate as the thickness increased from 18 to 24 plies.

The vacuum hose is placed on the bottom left corner of the square made from the sealant tape. Breather film is then placed on top of the stack up, making sure to cover the vacuum port as well as to allow for proper airflow from the laminate to the hose. A wider sheet of Thermalide film is then placed on top of the stack up and pressed down on the sealant tape to enclose the region of space for a vacuum to be established. Once the bagging film is in place, the Vacuubrand MD 1C pump is turned on to pull vacuum within the bagging space. The wires from the positive and negative terminals of the BK Precision 9201 power supply are attached to the copper tape strips now protruding from the exterior of the setup, which is now under vacuum pressure. Once the vacuum pressure reaches a value lower than 28.5 in. Hg, the power supply is turned on. The power output is managed from a graphical user interface of the manufacturer's software on the computer desktop via USB.

Figure 1: Temperature profile of OoO heated thermoplastic 18-ply thick laminate (in blue). The OoO's relatively precise temperature control allows one to closely follow the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle (MRCC) in red. Note: the 24-ply thick laminate to fabricate flex beam specimens had a dwell time of 40 minutes.

The autoclave 18- and 24-ply baseline plates (see cure cycles in Figs. 2 and 3) were made by Teijin Carbon America (the manufacturer) working with the University of Dayton Research Institute (UDRI), and the hot press baseline plates (see cure cycles in Figs. 4 and 5) were made at the manufacturer's facilities in Kettering, Ohio.

Figure 2: Autoclave 18-ply laminate plate temperature profile for producing SBS and DMA specimens. Note that temperature readings were lost in the cooling phase of the cure cycle and vacuum pressure is lost at ~80 minutes.

Figure 3: Autoclave 24-ply laminate plate temperature profile for producing 90° flex beam specimens. Note that temperature readings were lost in the heating and dwell phase of the cure cycle.

Figure 4: Hot press 18-ply laminate plate temperature profile for producing SBS and DMA samples. Note that the manufacturer did not record the pressure or vacuum conditions for this run.

Figure 5: Hot press 24-ply laminate plate temperature profile for producing 90° flex beam samples. Note that the manufacturer did not record the pressure or vacuum conditions for this run.

Two factors are crucial to determining the manufacturing quality and mechanical performance of the OoO cured specimens and their baseline (autoclave and hot press) counterparts: percent crystallinity and void content. Percent crystallinity is akin to the degree of cure for a thermoset resin but provides similar information for the curing of semi-crystalline matrices. Percent crystallinity measures the degree to which crystalline structures have formed in the matrix. Void content is also critical to assessing the quality of the composite, especially as it is a significant factor in the mechanical performance of a test specimen. Generally, the industry standard for aerospace-grade composites is having a void content of less than 2% of the total volume of the sample [3-5]. In some cases, this standard is lowered to 1% or less dependent on how critical the part is for the successful operation of a structure.

Manufacturing anomalies are noted in the autoclave cured baseline specimens that are expected to have an impact on laminate quality (this Section) and also mechanical properties in Figures 9 and 10.

In the SBS and DMA 18-ply specimens, an hour-long dwell time close to 400 °C is observed, and vacuum pressure is lost for most of the cure. In the 90° flex beam samples, vacuum is maintained, but the temperature data is lost such that the time at the dwell is actually not known. The long dwell time is probably present in the 90° flex beam samples as well given that the long dwell is due to the autoclaves inability to approach 400 °C as prescribed. The long dwell should have a positive impact on quality (and mechanical properties) while the loss of vacuum likely has a negative effect on both. Once the sample quality is determined and found to be acceptable for each set of specimens, the following experiments will be performed: SBS, DMA, and 90° flexural beam testing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed to determine the percent crystallinity of a cured sample. DSC is a thermoanalytical technique that relies on measuring the amount of heat required to raise the temperature of the sample compared to a reference. For this study, DSC analysis can reveal the percent crystallinity of a small cured sample of thermoplastic material. By heating a sample (weighing 4-10 mg) of HTS45/PEEK, one can measure the heat flux as a function of the temperature to generate a thermograph. As the temperature increases, there will be an endothermic peak around the melting point of PEEK, which is 342 °C [6]. By measuring the area underneath the curve of the endothermic peak on the thermograph, the enthalpy of the sample can be obtained. The heat of reaction is needed to calculate the percent crystallinity using the following well-known formula:

$$\text{Percent Crystallinity} = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_m^0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

ΔH_m represents the heat of reaction of the sample. ΔH_m^0 represents the heat of reaction of pure PEEK crystallized to 100%, or a fully crystalline PEEK sample. Literature shows that ΔH_m^0 for PEEK is 130 kJ/mol⁸². However, this equation has to be modified to reflect the matrix weight fraction of the thermoplastic prepreg, which is 34% according to the product data sheet for this material⁷². The modified equation is now:

$$\text{Percent Crystallinity} = \frac{\Delta H_m}{0.34 \cdot \Delta H_m^0} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

DSC samples were weighed on a mass balance, with the sample masses ranging from four to nine milligrams. The TA Instruments containers used to hold these samples were Tzero Aluminum Lids and Pans. These were also weighed on a mass balance. The masses for each sample, lid, and pan were recorded before the DSC experiments. The instrument used in these experiments was a TA Instruments Discovery DSC machine. The samples were loaded one by one into numbered trays in the sample bay of the machine. Then, the masses for the sample and the pan plus lid were entered into the respective boxes in the software for each run. The temperature cycle used was heating from 25 °C to 400 °C at 10 °C/min, followed by a 1-minute dwell at 400 °C, and then a cooling ramp back down to 25 °C at 5 °C/min. For this study, ten samples each for the OoO cured specimens, and the autoclave and hot press baseline specimens were tested via DSC. The results showed that the OoO specimens percent crystallinity ranged from 29 to 33 percent. The hot press specimens exhibited higher percent crystallinity of 35-37% as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: A boxplot of the percent crystallinities from each set of processing methods. Despite the considerable variation, these percent crystallinity values are within the manufacturer’s accepted range.

The manufacturer reports an ideal desired percent crystallinity range of 28-32%, which the OoO specimens' average crystallinity values fit within, and this range was the target of the processing cycle. However, the acceptable range from the manufacturer is noted to be 22-42% ($32\% \pm 10$) due to lack of process control in autoclaves and hot presses. With the percent crystallinity of the OoO specimens consistent with conventionally produced specimens and the manufacturer’s target range, examining the void content is the next critical step from a performance perspective to confirm the quality of these alternatively-cured test coupons. The void content in a composite laminate plays a significant role in its overall strength under load – the more voids in a composite, the greater the reduction in its mechanical strength. Voids allow stress concentrations to build up in the epoxy matrix, which is the weakest part of the laminate. These stress concentrations lead to cracks, which will propagate under increased mechanical loads. The cracks can result in delamination of the plies, causing the laminate to lose its stiffness and load-bearing capability.

A ZEISS Xradia 520 Versa 3D X-ray Microscope was used to image the microstructure of a scanned specimen, which allows the number of voids to be quantified in a given test coupon. Depending on the type of specimen (SBS, DMA, or 90° flex), a metal stand was used to hold the specimen in place. The stand was placed on a stage within the interior of the Versa, where it would rotate in front of the source to have X-rays penetrate it and capture the resulting images through the detector. For longer specimens such as the DMA or 90° flex beam, the Stitch option was used to scan sections of the coupon and then “stitch” them together after all of the sections were individually captured.

For each method (OoO, autoclave, and hot press), two SBS/DMA (the specimens came from the same plate) and five 90° flex beam specimens were scanned in the Versa microscope. The objective used was 0.4X for all of the specimens except the last specimen from each curing method’s set. The parameters for the 0.4X scans were as follows: voltage set to 60 kV, power set to 5 W, and the pixel size of 4.8 μm . The 0.4X scans are primarily for checking the void content of the scanned specimens. The last specimen of each set was scanned using an objective of 4X, which decreased the pixel size to roughly 1.5 μm , while still maintaining a power of 5 W and a voltage of 60 kV, allowing the individual fibers to be seen inside the matrix in each ply. Once the specimens were scanned, the images depicting their microstructure were opened in ImageJ, the imaging software used for Versa-scanned specimens. The color contrast was adjusted to only focus on two different peaks; the first peak represented the voids in the image, and the second peak corresponded to the fiber-matrix consisting of the rest of the picture. By isolating these two peaks, the area of the voids could be manually counted in Image J, and then divided by the area of the whole image to obtain the void content for a single image.

This was done for twenty images for each specimen with standard error calculated. Images of the SBS/DMA specimens from the 18-ply autoclave, hot press, and OoO plates are shown in Figure 7 at the 1.5 μm pixel resolution, with the data summarized in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Microcomputed tomography images of the following specimens: upper left: 18-ply SBS/DMA autoclave specimen, upper middle: 18-ply SBS/DMA hot press specimen, upper right: 18-ply SBS/DMA OoO specimen, lower left: 24-ply 90° flex beam autoclave specimen, lower middle: 24-ply 90° flex hot press specimen, lower right: 24-ply 90° flex OoO specimen. The darker gray regions are the voids shown in red, and the blue circles identify the resin-rich regions in light gray that have an absence of microfibers.

The storage modulus curves from the DMA testing, including the representative curves in the left graph in Figure 9, were used to determine the T_g for each set of specimens shown in the right graph of Figure 9. While the tan delta curves could have been used as well, the storage modulus curves are preferred in this case due to their conservativeness [7]. The right graph in Figure 9 shows the T_g for each set of SBS/DMA specimens. The mean T_g values for the autoclave, hot press, and OoO specimens are 139 °C, 136 °C, and 140 °C, respectively. It is important to note that these values, particularly the autoclave and OoO specimens, are close to the reported value from the manufacturer, which is 143 °C.

In the 90° flexural testing, the hot press and OoO specimens are statistically the same, while the autoclave specimens outperform the two significantly (see the left graph of Fig. 10). The main observation from the 90° flexural testing is that the autoclave specimens have significantly higher mean strength values of 207 MPa compared to the hot press and OoO mean strength values of 150 MPa and 152 MPa, respectively, as shown in Figure 10. The main explanation for the autoclave flex specimens outperforming the other two sets of specimens is the extended dwell time (over an hour) at 400 °C of the laminate plate from which the specimens were produced. The thermal inertia of the

autoclave used resulted in a thermal lag between the air temperature and the laminate temperature. This temperature gradient of 10 °C within the autoclave required the dwell time to be extended by roughly one hour to allow the laminate to reach 400 °C. The extra time needed to allow the laminate to reach the correct dwell temperature naturally allows for more consolidation of the plies and greatly reduces the void content and resin-rich regions in the composite material. The lower void content of the autoclave flex specimens shown in Figure 8 is attributed to the extended dwell time, thus resulting in an increased flexural strength. Unlike the 18-ply autoclave laminate processing, vacuum pressure was maintained throughout the duration of the cure cycle for the 24-ply autoclave laminate. The hot press and OoO specimens, while lower in mean flexural strength, show no statistical difference between one another, showing the latter heating method’s capability to match the conventional technique to process thermoplastic materials.

As opposed to the 90° flexural test results in shown in the left graph, Figure 10, the OoO specimens outperformed the hot press and autoclave samples in SBS, surpassing the latter by a significant margin (see Fig. 10, right graph). The autoclave results can be explained by the large voids in the autoclave SBS/DMA samples, which reduce the strength. As noted previously, vacuum pressure was lost shortly after the first hour of the cure cycle of the 18-ply laminate (see Fig. 3), while it was maintained for the duration 24-ply laminate’s cure cycle (see Fig. 4). As seen in the flexural testing results, the hot press and OoO specimens show no statistical difference between the two, with the latter’s mean short beam shear strength value being 130 MPa and the former’s only 120 MPa.

Figure 8: Left graph: comparison of void content percentage of each of the different processing methods of the 18-ply SBS/DMA laminates with their standard error (SE). Right graph: Comparison of void content percentage of each of the different processing methods for the 24-ply laminates.

Figure 9: Left graph: Representative storage modulus, loss modulus, and tan delta curves for the autoclave, hot press, and OoO SBS/DMA specimens at a frequency of 1 Hz. Right graph: A comparison of the respective T_g for each processing method calculated from the storage modulus of the specimens.

Figure 10: Left graph: The comparison of the 90° flexural beam test results of the different processing methods. Right graph: SBS test results of the different processing methods.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The Thermal Stability and Max Temperature Tests validated the efficacy of the commercial CNT film to maintain the processing temperature of 400 °C for thirty to forty minutes as required by the MRCC for VBO production. The commercial CNT film was then used to produce OoO SBS, DMA, and 90° flex beam specimens to compare against their conventional autoclave and hot press counterparts. Autoclave-processed specimens had noted issues with the actual vs. desired cure cycles and for comparison purposes need to be re-manufactured. Quality checks showed that OoO specimens had acceptable percent crystallinity values that were within the manufacturer's targeted range. Microcomputed tomography images showed acceptably low void content (~0.1%) for the SBS and DMA samples when compared with the hot press-made samples, and the OoO 90° flex beam specimen void content was also consistent with the hot press counterparts. DMA tests also showed that OoO samples had similar T_g values to their hot press counterparts. Mechanical testing revealed that OoO processing outperforms the hot press samples by significant margins. This study has shown that OoO heating appears to produce equivalent thermoplastic parts when compared to conventional methods

such as hot press consolidation. OoO heating may have advantages in consistently producing aerospace-grade thermoplastic structures with complex geometries, but further work is needed to substantiate this with additional data on properly manufactured autoclave specimens.

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